

High throughput laser surface micro-structuring of polystyrene by combining direct laser interference patterning with polygon scanner technology

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ABSTRACT

Laser-based processing techniques have proven to be an effective option of modifying polymer surfaces. In this context Direct Laser Interference Patterning in conjunction with the polygon scanner technique is used to fabricate textured polystyrene surfaces through ultra-fast beam deflection. This is achieved by using a high-average power picosecond laser in combination with a polygon mirror-based scanning system. The two-beam DLIP optical configuration leads to the formation of line-like structures with a spatial period of 21.0 μm . The influence of the scanning speed and the repetition rate on the structure formation is investigated, allowing structure heights up to 23 μm . The formation of the micro-structure was found to result from swelling and ablation mechanisms. By applying scanning speeds of 350 m/s, a throughput of 1.1 m^2/min is reported for the first time using this method.

Introduction

Surface modification of polymer materials is a useful way to obtain surface functionalities by producing well-defined topographical elements or modifying their chemistry. This increases the potential range of applications in the fields of microfluidics, biomedical applications, electronics as well as allowing the fabrication of decorative motives, or to provide self-cleaning or antibacterial surfaces [1,2].

In particular laser-micro structuring is considered to be a flexible and highly versatile solution for producing functionalized polymer surfaces, being one of the available technologies Direct Laser Interference Patterning (DLIP). DLIP is an innovative method for generating periodic and deterministic microstructures. In this process, coherent laser beams are superimposed on a substrate's surface, leading to the formation of an interference pattern with a periodic distribution of the laser intensity [3]. Furthermore, controlling the number of the applied laser beams and their overlapping angles, allows producing specific geometries and sizes, which can be directly transferred to the material's surface by local ablation processes at the interference maxima.

In previous studies, DLIP was applied to produce periodic line-like structures on black dyed polycarbonate [4]. The investigations revealed that the resulting structure formation is characterized by

swelling mechanisms in addition to material ablation.

For gaining the accessibility onto an industrial level, different beam manipulation systems have been developed to increase the process throughput. For example, using a static DLIP optical concept with an elongated beam profile, it was possible to produce line-like structures with a maximal throughput of 0.90 m^2/min on polycarbonate, by translating the substrate at ~ 1 m/s [5]. Other technologies, such as polygon scanners allow speeds up to 1000 m/s without the necessity of translating the parts, but with relative low resolutions ($\sim 40\text{--}50$ μm) [6]. The aim of this work is to demonstrate the feasibility of combining polygon scanners with DLIP technique, increasing both resolution as well as throughputs reaching values of at least 1 m^2/min .

Material and methods

The laser structuring trials were carried out on 1.5 mm thick polystyrene plates. Prior to the laser structuring process, the surface was cleaned with ethanol to remove impurities. The DLIP process was carried out using a picosecond laser (EdgeWave, Germany) emitting at the fundamental wavelength of 1064 nm with a pulse duration of 10 ps. The used optical configuration (see Fig. 1) produces an interference pattern from two laser beams at the focal plane, leading to the formation of line-

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like structures with a spatial period Λ of 21.0 μm (Interference angle $\Theta = 2.9^\circ$). Further explanation in more detail of the physical mechanism of DLIP were published elsewhere [3,5]. To achieve high scanning speeds along the surface of the substrate a polygon scanner (Moewe, Germany) was utilized with a double-reflecting polygon mirror architecture. The deflected sub-beams were focused onto the material surface by a 420-mm f-theta objective lens, generating a spot diameter of 75 μm and enabling a maximum scan field of $300 \times 300 \text{ mm}^2$. To produce surface patterns with different structure heights, the scanning speed v_{scan} was varied from 50 to 350 m/s and the repetition rate f_{rep} was changed from 2 to 5 MHz. In all cases, the maximal available laser power was used (470 W). It is worth to mention, that the optical efficiency of the used DOE is 85%, which means that 15% of the used laser power is lost in the process of interference generation.

For investigating the surface topography of the laser-structured samples, confocal microscopic images (Sensofar S-Neox, Spain) were recorded. In addition, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was employed (Zeiss Supra 40VP, Germany) for a more detailed analysis of the surface topography.

Results and discussion

In a first set of experiments, a broad screening of the process parameters (scanning speed v_{scan} , laser repetition rate f_{rep}) was performed to investigate the variation of the structure morphology. In this way, the total energy applied per unit of area (cumulated laser fluence Φ_{cum}) can be controlled for a fix laser power ($\sim 470 \text{ W}$) and different surface topographies can be produced, as shown in Fig. 2. The cumulated fluence is calculated by:

$$\Phi_{\text{cum}} = \frac{E_{\text{pulse}}}{\text{Area}_{\text{spot}}} \cdot \text{Number}_{\text{pulses}}$$

$$E_{\text{pulse}} = \frac{P_{\text{laser}}}{f_{\text{rep}}} \cdot \text{Number}_{\text{pulses}} = \frac{v_{\text{scan}}}{f_{\text{rep}}}$$

The pulse energy was varied between 90 and 230 μJ , resulting in a laser fluence per pulse of 2.12 Jcm^{-2} and 5.86 Jcm^{-2} , respectively. Note that in SEM images of Fig. 2a and b several scanned lines (with the DLIP features) have been used to process the sample. The scanned lines are separated by a distance of 75.0 μm . Single lines produced by this configuration are depicted in the confocal images of Fig. 2d-f, where three interference maxima were obtained within the laser spot.

Using a scanning speed of 200 m/s (Fig. 2a and d) and a repetition rate of 5 MHz (resulting in $\Phi_{\text{cum}} = 2.8 \text{ J/cm}^2$), well-defined periodic lines were produced, which result from the local swelling of the polymer material at the positions corresponding to the maxima of the interference pattern. Heights of 6.0 μm were obtained. The black dye is responsible for the swelling of the polymer, which absorbs the IR radiation and leads to the production of gaseous by-products forming inner pores below the polymer surface as already reported [6].

For higher cumulated laser fluences of Φ_{cum} of 4.2 and 8.3 J/cm^2 (obtained at scanning speeds v_{scan} of 150 and 100 m/s, respectively) the treated areas show a stronger modification of the material surface, obtaining features with heights between 5 μm and 12 μm . In this case, the structure formation is driven through a combination of swelling and ablation process (Fig. 2b, e and c, f).

The dependency of the resulting structure height with the applied scanning speed at different repetition rates (2 to 5 MHz) is shown in Fig. 3a. As it can be seen, similar structure heights were obtained in particular at scanning speeds from 150 to 350 m/s for all used repetition rates. In this case, the structure height ranged from approximately 3 to 6 μm . Furthermore, slight deviations in the height of the structures were observed (see error bars) indicating a homogeneous surface topography.

The largest structure heights were achieved for a scanning speed of 50 m/s, ranging from ~ 12 to 23 μm . Whereby the resulting structure height values for the respective repetition rates show a large deviation, denoting a higher irregularity of the surface topography. The negative dependency of the structure height with the scanning speed can be explained by the cumulated laser fluence. If slower scanning speeds are applied, more pulses are used to irradiate a certain area and thus higher amount of the polymer is swelled at the maxima positions. On the other hand, higher repetition rates led to higher structures, which means that pulses with lower fluences are more efficient to swell the structures.

The material throughput has been calculated taking into consideration the scanning speed, the separation distance between the scanned lines and the duty cycle of the polygon ($\sim 50\%$). Throughput rates of 0.11 and 0.79 m^2/min were obtained for the scanning speeds of 50 and 350 m/s, respectively and a line separation distance of 75 μm . By increasing the separation distance up to 100 μm , a throughput of 1.1 m^2/min was reached. An example of a polymer surface ($150 \times 150 \text{ mm}^2$) treated at 350 m/s can be seen in Fig. 3b. In this case, the separation distance between the scanned lines was 100 μm . When evaluating the surface topography by confocal microscopy, the individual scanned lines (with the DLIP pattern) are visible (Fig. 3c), since the used distance between the lines was larger than the spot size. In addition, the interference maxima can be distinguished in each scanned line.

In the future, new optical designs are necessary to obtain significant shorter spatial periods (e.g. 5–10 μm), since smaller features can result on enhanced functionalities. This is today not possible with conventional polygon scanner due to relative small polygon mirrors used as well as their limited aperture size, allowing small interference angles.

Conclusion

In this work, the combination of Direct Laser Interference Patterning and polygon scanner technologies was demonstrated for the first time. Using a high-power picosecond laser source, black polystyrene plates were treated at scanning speeds between 50 and 350 m/s, showing the viability of the process. Line-like patterns with a spatial period of 21.0 μm and structure heights up to 23 μm were produced on the polymer

Fig. 1. Schematic drawing of the used experimental configuration with the polygon scanner unit in combination with two-beam interference optics.

Fig. 2. SEM images (a–c) and corresponding 3D confocal measurements (d–f) of DLIP structured polystyrene at a repetition rate f_{rep} of 5 MHz and different scanning speeds: $\Phi_{\text{cum}} = 2.8 \text{ J/cm}^2$, $v_{\text{scan}} = 200 \text{ m/s}$ (a, d); $\Phi_{\text{cum}} = 4.2 \text{ J/cm}^2$, $v_{\text{scan}} = 150 \text{ m/s}$ (b, e); $\Phi_{\text{cum}} = 8.3 \text{ J/cm}^2$, $v_{\text{scan}} = 100 \text{ m/s}$ (c, f); spatial period $\Lambda = 21.0 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 3. Structure height in dependence of scanning speed and repetition rates f_{rep} and corresponding throughput (a); optical image of $150 \times 150 \text{ mm}^2$ treated polymer surface at 350 m/s (b) and its corresponding confocal image showing 20 scanned lines on an area of $2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^2$ (c).

material, induced either by the local swelling of the material at low cumulated fluences, or by a combination of ablation and swelling at higher fluences. The method allowed reaching outstanding throughputs up to 1.1 m²/min.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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